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Kamianets-Podilskyi, Ukraine***Abstract**

The article examines the main principles of renewable energy development in European countries; the practice of the EU regarding energy efficiency and the development of renewable energy was analyzed; modern trends and development potential of «green» energy in Ukraine are summarized; the essence of state management of the development of renewable energy in the European Union is revealed; a set of economic mechanisms for stimulating the development of «green» energy in Ukraine is analyzed.

Keywords: «green» energy, renewable energy sources, energy efficiency, stimulating the development of renewable energy, energy efficiency policy.

Green energy is an energy industry that uses renewable energy sources and technologies to reduce the impact on the environment compared to traditional energy sources such as coal, oil and natural gas.

The main sources of «green» energy include:

- solar energy;
- wind energy;
- hydropower;
- biomass and biofuel;
- geothermal energy.

These technologies are becoming more and more efficient and competitive compared to traditional energy sources, which allows them to become more popular and widespread. They also help reduce dependence on carbon and other harmful emissions, helping to reduce the greenhouse gas effect and conserve natural resources.

The development of renewable energy in the European Union (EU) is one of the key priorities within the strategy to combat climate change and ensure energy security. The EU has set ambitious targets for renewable energy and adopted a number of legislative acts to stimulate its development. Here are some key aspects of renewable energy development in the EU:

- Renewable energy targets: The EU has set ambitious targets for renewable energy, in particular, achieving a percentage of renewable energy in the overall energy mix. For example, the European Commission has set a target, according to which by 2030 the goal of using renewable energy at the level of at least 32% of the total energy consumption in the EU should be achieved.

- Incentive mechanisms: The EU uses a variety of mechanisms to stimulate the development of renewable energy, such as financial support systems, renewable energy tariffs, tax credits, emissions trading schemes, as well as various programs and initiatives to support research and development.

- Infrastructure: The EU is actively working on the development of appropriate infrastructure for the production and transmission of renewable energy, such

as solar farms, wind farms, hydroelectric power plants, etc., as well as storage and transmission systems.

- Innovation and research: The EU also invests in research and innovation in the field of renewable energy, directing resources to develop new technologies and increase their efficiency.

- Political support and international cooperation: the EU actively cooperates with other countries and international organizations to jointly develop renewable energy and reduce the impact on climate change.

As a result of these efforts, the European Union is a world leader in the development of renewable energy and continues to actively promote this agenda both domestically and internationally.

In recent years, the EU has seen a steady increase in the share of renewable energy sources. In particular, it is 30,75% in electricity production, 19,48% in heating and cooling, and 7,42% in the transport sector. In some sectors, the share of renewable energy in electricity, heating and cooling systematically exceeds the targets set by European countries in their National Action Plans. In the transport sector, these indicators mostly correspond to the planned ones. The level of use of renewable energy sources reflects the historical diversity of the energy systems of the member states and their potential in the field of renewable energy, varying from 6,4% in Luxembourg to 54,5% in Sweden [1].

Investments in renewable energy sources in EU countries are increasingly subject to market conditions, while the share of state support and subsidies is decreasing. This is due to a significant reduction in the cost of renewable energy technologies and a reduction in subsidies due to more competitive support schemes. Current policy and planned initiatives in the field of renewable energy may prove insufficient for the timely achievement of national mandatory targets in a number of European countries. In this context, there is a new mobilization of efforts at all levels and throughout the EU, in particular thanks to the activities of the special task force on energy efficiency.

The European Union's policy on energy efficiency and the use of renewable energy sources is one of the most ambitious and progressive in the world. The European Commission and EU member states are actively working on the development and implementation of strategies and measures to increase energy efficiency and reduce emissions of harmful gases through the development of renewable energy sources. Here are some key EU practices in these areas:

- Energy efficiency standards: The EU sets mandatory energy efficiency standards for various types of products and devices, including electrical appliances, cars, building materials and others. This helps reduce energy consumption and carbon emissions.

- Financial incentives: The European Commission provides financial support for energy efficiency projects and initiatives through various programs and funds. This may include subsidies, concessional loans, grants and other financing instruments.

- Building policy: The EU sets energy efficiency standards for buildings and encourages the introduction of innovative technologies that help reduce energy consumption and improve energy efficiency.

- Increasing the share of renewable energy sources: the European Union is constantly working on increasing the share of renewable energy sources in the energy mix. This includes the development of wind, solar, hydropower and other sources.

- Stimulating research and innovation: the EU provides support for research and development of new technologies in the field of energy efficiency and renewable energy sources, which promotes the emergence of new solutions and improves their availability.

These practices help reduce energy dependence, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, increase competitiveness, and create new clean energy markets and jobs.

Increasing energy efficiency in EU countries is considered the most cost-effective way to strengthen energy security and reduce greenhouse gas emissions. Energy efficiency policy is one of the main elements of the climate package of measures «Readiness-55». On September 20, 2023, the updated Energy Efficiency Directive was published, significantly raising the EU's ambitions in this area.

Energy efficiency is one of five key aspects to be included in National Energy and Climate Plans. Ukraine, as a candidate country for joining the EU, is also developing its National Energy and Climate Plan. Special attention to energy efficiency policy is necessary due to significant destruction of the country's energy infrastructure, a possible energy shortage, and the urgent need to develop measures after the moratorium on raising tariffs for energy (utility) services is lifted [2].

Ukraine has great potential for the development of «green» energy due to its natural resources and technological capabilities. Some current trends and potential for green energy development in Ukraine include:

- Solar energy: Ukraine has great potential for the production of solar energy, particularly in the south and southwest of the country. Several large solar power plants have been launched in recent years, but there is potential for further development of the sector.

- Wind energy: Ukraine also has significant potential for the use of wind energy, in particular on the coast of the Black and Azov seas. The first wind farms have recently been launched and the sector is constantly developing.

- Hydropower: Ukraine has the potential to develop hydropower on rivers and ponds. Although there are limitations due to hydro-ecological factors, water energy can still be a significant source of «green» energy.

- Biomass and biogas: Ukraine has significant potential for the use of biomass and biogas for the production of electricity and heat. This may include the use of agricultural waste, sewage and other biological resources.

- Energy efficiency: The development of «green» energy also includes increasing energy efficiency in all sectors of the economy. Ukraine can take advantage of opportunities to modernize industrial and residential buildings, introduce energy-efficient technologies, and encourage energy conservation.

To develop «green» energy in Ukraine, a stable investment and legal framework is needed, as well as government support to create favorable conditions for investors in renewable energy sources. Such measures can contribute not only to the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions, but also to ensure energy security and create new jobs.

On April 21, 2023, the Government of Ukraine approved the new Energy Strategy of the country until 2050 (Order No. 373-r). The main goal of the strategy is to transform Ukraine into the energy hub of Europe. To achieve this, it is planned to significantly increase generation capacity from renewable sources by 2050: wind power up to 140 GW (with investments of about \$134 billion), solar power up to 94 GW (\$62 billion), energy storage up to 38 GW (\$25 billion), nuclear generation up to 30 GW (\$80 billion), CHP and bioenergy plants up to 18 GW, and hydro generation up to 9 GW (\$4.5 billion).

Thus, Ukraine has an official document that envisages ambitious plans for the transformation of the energy sector through the development of renewable and carbon-neutral energy sources, as well as the attraction of investments in the energy sector. The main emphasis is on private foreign and Ukrainian investments [3].

State management of the development of renewable energy in the EU is based on a comprehensive strategy that includes legislative initiatives, financial support, stimulation of innovation and other measures to promote the transition to clean energy. Here are some key aspects of state management of the development of renewable energy in the European Union:

- Strategic planning: the EU develops strategies and documents defining key goals and objectives in the field of renewable energy, such as the European Energy and Climate Action Plan, which contains targets for reducing CO₂ emissions and increasing the share of renewable energy.

- Legislative initiatives: The European Commission adopts legislation stimulating the development

of renewable energy, such as the Renewable Energy Directive, which sets mandatory targets for the use of renewable energy in EU member states.

- Financial support: The EU provides financial support for the development of renewable energy through various instruments such as funds, grants, loans and other financial mechanisms.

- Innovation and research: The European Union actively invests in research and development of new technologies in the field of renewable energy, which contributes to the emergence of new solutions and increasing their efficiency.

- Monitoring and reporting: the EU monitors the implementation of renewable energy targets and reports on progress in this area, allowing timely adjustments of strategies and measures.

These measures allow the European Union to effectively manage the process of building renewable energy, contributing to the transition to a sustainable and ecologically clean energy future.

The legal basis for the development of renewable energy in Europe is based on directives developed by the European Commission, approved by the European Parliament and adopted by the Council of Europe. The rapid growth of this sector of the economy has been made possible by legally binding targets for increasing the share of energy from renewable sources, established by Directive 2009/28/EU on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources. In 2018, Directive 2018/2001/EC was adopted, which also promotes the development of renewable energy. The new regulatory framework foresees a mandatory goal for the EU by 2030 – the achievement of 32% of energy from renewable sources [4].

Ukraine uses various economic mechanisms to stimulate the development of «green» energy. Some of them include:

- Renewable energy tariffs: the government sets guaranteed tariffs for electricity generation using renewable energy sources such as solar, wind, hydro and biomass. This encourages investors to develop renewable energy projects.

- Grants and subsidies: The government provides financial support in the form of grants and subsidies to renewable energy producers or other market participants who invest in this area. This may include assistance in preparing projects, raising loans, developing research, etc.

- Green electricity tariff for consumers: The government can set preferential electricity tariffs for consumers who use «green» energy. This stimulates the demand for clean energy and promotes the development of the renewable energy market.

- Emissions trading schemes: the inclusion of sectors that produce electricity from renewable sources in the CO₂ emissions trading system can stimulate investment in green energy by creating financial incentives to reduce emissions.

- Encouraging energy efficiency: the government can establish programs and initiatives to encourage energy efficiency, such as incentives for installing energy-saving equipment or energy-efficient mechanisms.

In 2023, the President of Ukraine signed the Law «On Amendments to Certain Laws of Ukraine Regarding the Restoration and «Green» Transformation of the Energy System of Ukraine» which is aimed at developing small-scale generation from alternative energy sources and improving conditions for supporting green energy in the country.

The main initiatives of this Law include:

1. Implementation of certificates of origin of energy from renewable sources and biomethane, which will allow tracking the sources and amount of green energy used. This promotes transparency and support for environmentally friendly energy sources.

2. The possibility of exporting energy from renewable sources, which gives Ukrainian producers access to foreign markets. This supports the development of Ukrainian green energy and strengthens the country's position in international relations.

3. Implementation of the «feed-in-premium» model, which stimulates the holding of auctions for the distribution of support quotas for commercial projects of renewable energy sources (RES). This creates a competitive environment for the implementation of new projects and increases the share of green energy in the country's energy balance.

4. Granting RES producers the right to independently sell their electricity on the market, which provides greater flexibility in interaction with energy units. This promotes diversity of suppliers, increases efficiency and stimulates innovation in the field of renewable energy.

5. Implementation of the «Net Billing» option, which allows households to install their own generation facilities and sell excess electricity at market prices. This encourages active participation of citizens in the production of green energy, reduces dependence on traditional energy sources and stimulates local production of green energy [5].

These economic mechanisms contribute to the development of «green» energy in Ukraine, stimulating investments and consumption of ecologically clean energy, which contributes to the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and dependence on the import of energy resources.

Conclusions. The strategic development of renewable energy sources brings significant environmental benefits that are important for sustainable development. The transition from coal and gas generation will allow Ukraine to achieve the climate goals of the Paris Agreement, reducing air and water pollution. However, the development of «green» energy is still held back by high capital investments, unstable politics, bureaucratic obstacles and infrastructure problems related to the modernization of outdated distribution networks. Targeted interventions in governance, financing, infrastructure and capacity building can help overcome these barriers. Accelerating the development of renewable energy requires investments in the sustainable future of Ukraine, which will contribute to environmental sustainability and social stability. Leadership in the transition to clean energy will lead the economy and society of Ukraine to the path of socially balanced and ecologically conscious development, which will meet

the goals of sustainable development and will become a key element of the country's post-war recovery.

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